

Condensation of 3- and 4-Nitrophthalic Anhydrides with Phenol and Anisole.

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Of the various methods available for the synthesis of hydroxy-anthraquinones, the condensation of nitrophthalic anhydrides with phenols and phenol ethers and the subsequent conversion of the resulting nitrobenzoylbenzoic acids into amino- and hydroxybenzoylbenzoic acids followed by ring-closing, is one of the most fruitful.

When phthalic anhydride condenses with phenols, the condensation takes place in such a way that the hydroxyl groups preferably take up the *ortho*-position with respect to the CO-group, though the *para*-linking also takes place to a limited extent. With phenolic ethers, however, linking is invariably in the *para*-position with respect to the alkyloxy group. In the case of nitrophthalic anhydrides a further complication is introduced by the presence of the nitro group, which exerts its own orienting influence. The present study was undertaken to ascertain the effect of such influence.

The following table gives the results of the condensation of 3- and 4-nitrophthalic anhydrides with benzene and toluene as determined by previous workers.

Components reacting.	Products obtained.	Authors and reference.,
	Rainer, <i>Monatsch.</i> 1908, 29, 178.	
	Mitter and Sircar, <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1930, 7, 619.	
	<i>ibid.</i>	
	Mitter and Goswami, <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1931, 8, 686.	

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It would appear from the above that in the case of condensations with hydrocarbons, the CO-group nearer to the nitro group is more reactive than the other. The second component exerts little influence. Its influence becomes more marked, however, when the hydrocarbons are replaced by molecules having reactive groupings.

The following results have been obtained by previous workers in the condensations of 3- and 4-nitrophthalic anhydrides with phenols.

Components reacting.	Products obtained.	Authors and reference.
		Eder and Widmer, <i>Helv. Chim. Acta</i> , 1922, 8, 3.
and		
		Mitter and Chatterjee, <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1931, 8, 784.
and		

It may be observed that in the case of condensation with 3-nitrophthalic anhydride, the quantity of the second isomer is very small in comparison with that of the first one.

3-Nitrophthalic anhydride condenses with phenol in presence of aluminium chloride at 110-20° under the conditions employed by Eder and Widmer (*loc. cit.*) to give only one product, which may be one of the following four :—

To determine the actual constitution, the nitro-acid is reduced to the corresponding amino-acid and then converted to the corresponding dihydroxy-acid by diazotisation. On heating with concentrated sulphuric acid and boric acid at the temperature of boiling water, the latter gave a dihydroxyanthraquinone identical with chryszazine. The constitution of the nitro-acid must therefore be (I).

Curiously enough, 4-nitrophthalic anhydride could not be condensed with phenol under any condition.

3-Nitrophthalic anhydride condenses readily with anisole with the formation of two products (V) and (VI), the former predominating.

The constitution of the first isomer was determined by converting it into 1:5-dihydroxyanthraquinone of Frobenius and Hepp (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1048). The quantity of the other isomer being very small, its constitution could not be determined in the usual way by conversion into the corresponding dihydroxyanthraquinone. The constitution (VI) has been ascribed to it on the ground that while (V) easily gives the methyl ester by Victor Meyer's method, the second isomer was recovered unchanged even after refluxing for 2 hours with a methyl alcoholic solution of hydrochloric acid.

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4-Nitrophthalic anhydride condenses with anisole at 20-25° in presence of aluminium chloride to give

Their constitutions have been determined in the usual way by conversions to 2:6- and 2:7-dihydroxyanthraquinones respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3-Nitro-2-(2'-hydroxy)-benzoylbenzoic Acid.—3-Nitrophthalic anhydride (10 g.) was dissolved in redistilled phenol (100 c.c.) and heated to 110°-120° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. Powdered aluminium chloride (20 g.) was gradually added and the mixture occasionally shaken. It was heated at 135° for 2 $\frac{1}{2}$ —3 hours when the mass almost solidified. It was decomposed with ice-water, hydrochloric acid (135 c.c., 10%) was added and heated on a water-bath; the excess of phenol was steam-distilled and the solid black mass was filtered and boiled with calcium carbonate repeatedly and the hot filtrate acidified with hydrochloric acid when the acid was precipitated. It was crystallised from dilute acetic acid as small yellow needles, m.p. 237-38°; yield 5-6 g. (Found: N, 4.97. C₁₄H₉O₄N requires N, 4.87 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by heating with acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine, crystallised from glacial acetic acid in shining colourless needles, m.p. 158°. (Found: N, 4.29. C₁₆H₁₁O₇N requires N, 4.25 per cent.)

The *methyl ester*, obtained by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas into methyl alcoholic solution of benzoylbenzoic acid (1.5 g.) and refluxing on a water-bath for an hour, crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 162°. (Found: N, 4.85. C₁₅H₁₁O₆N requires N, 4.65 per cent).

3-Amino-2-(2'-hydroxy)-benzoylbenzoic Acid.—A warm solution of the nitrobenzoylbenzoic acid (4.5 g.) in concentrated ammonia (45 c.c.) was added to freshly precipitated ferrous hydroxide obtained from ferrous sulphate (32 g. in 210 c.c. of water and 50 c.c. of ammonia) and the mixture heated for 15 minutes and filtered. The filtrate was boiled to drive off ammonia and the solution boiled with a hot solution of alum (4.5 g. in 45 c.c. of water) and filtered, when

prismatic yellow crystals (2 g.) were obtained. It was recrystallised from water, m.p. 217° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.36. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 5.44 per cent).

3-Hydroxy-2-(2'-hydroxy)-benzoylbenzoic Acid.—The amino-acid (2 g.) was dissolved in dilute ammonia by warming and dilute hydrochloric acid added until the precipitate first formed dissolved and on cooling, the hydrochloride was obtained in fine suspension. It was cooled and diazotised with a solution of sodium nitrite (0.7 g.). The precipitated diazo-salt was decomposed by boiling for 10-15 minutes, a little animal charcoal added and the solution filtered hot, when silky yellow needles (1.5 g.) were obtained. It was recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 199°-200°. It gives light pink colour with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 64.77; H, 4.12. $C_{14}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 65.1; H, 3.86 per cent).

The *diacetyl* derivative, prepared by heating with acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine for 3 hours, was crystallised from alcohol in colourless silky crystals, m.p. 186°. (Found: C, 62.98; H, 4.25. $C_{18}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 63.1; H, 4.09 per cent).

1:8-Dihydroxyanthraquinone (chryszazin).—The dihydroxy-acid (2g.) was mixed with boric anhydride (2 g.), sulphuric acid (4 g., *d.*, 1.84) and fuming sulphuric acid (20 g., 20% SO_3) and the mixture heated on a water-bath for 3 hours. This was then poured into ice and the orange mass was extracted with boiling water to remove boric acid and then with a cold 5% solution of sodium carbonate and finally crystallised from glacial acetic acid as bright golden yellow needles, m.p. 190-91° (*lit.* m.p. 191°). (Found: C, 70.45; H, 3.46. Calc. for $C_{14}H_8O_4$: C, 70.00; H, 3.33 per cent).

The *diacetyl* derivative crystallised from absolute alcohol as white needles, m.p. 230-32° (*lit.* m.p. 227-31°).

Condensation of Anisole with 3-Nitrophthalic Anhydride.

3-Nitrophthalic anhydride (10 g.) and anisole (100 c.c.) were treated in the cold under stirring with aluminium chloride (20 g.) and the mixture left overnight at the ordinary temperature. The deep red viscous mass was decomposed with ice-cold water and dilute hydrochloric acid and the excess of anisole distilled off with steam. The black tarry mass was extracted with dilute alkali, precipitated with acid, washed and boiled with calcium carbonate. The filtrate was acidified, and the red precipitate was dried and refluxed with benzene

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to remove the tarry product when an insoluble portion was left as flaky crystals. It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 214-15° (yield 0.9 g. from 10 g. of the mixture). The mother liquor was diluted with water and the precipitate crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 207° (yield 6-7 g. from 10 g. of the mixture).

3-Nitro-2-(4'-methoxy)-benzoylbenzoic Acid, (m. p. 207°) [Found: N, 4.25; OMe, 10.67. $C_{14}H_9O_5N(OMe)$ requires N, 4.6; OMe, 10.3 per cent].

The *methyl ester* melts at 123°. (Found: N, 4.69. $C_{16}H_{13}O_6N$ requires N, 4.44 per cent).

3-Amino-2-(4'-methoxy)-benzoylbenzoic Acid.—A warm solution of nitrobenzoylbenzoic acid (4.5 g.) in concentrated ammonia (45 c.c.) was added to the precipitated ferrous hydroxide from ferrous sulphate (32 g. in 210 c.c. of water and 50 c.c. of ammonia) and the mixture heated for 15 minutes and filtered. To the boiling solution a hot solution of alum was added and the solution filtered hot, when yellow crystals separated. It was recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 169-70°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 5.16. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 5.18 per cent).

3-Hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxy)-benzoylbenzoic Acid.—The diazonium salt of the amino-acid was decomposed as usual and on filtration yellow needles with slight tarry matter were obtained. The crystals were washed with ether and recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 211-13°, yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 4.60. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.7; H, 4.42 per cent).

1:6-Dihydroxyanthraquinone.—The crude anthraquinone was obtained by heating on a water-bath for 3 hours the above benzoylbenzoic acid (1 g.), boric anhydride (1 g.), sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 2 g. and 20% SO_3 , 10 g) and removing the boric acid with boiling water and 5% sodium carbonate. It was intimately mixed with aluminium chloride (1 g.) and heated to 230° in the course of one hour and then kept at this temperature for half an hour more (*cf.* Mitter and Sircar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 628). The cold mixture was poured into acidified water and the residue dissolved in caustic potash and acidified. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 270-73°; diacetyl derivative, m.p. 230-4°.

6-Nitro-2-(4'-methoxy)-benzoylbenzoic Acid, m. p. 215°. (Found: N, 5.0; $C_{15}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 4.7 per cent).

6-Amino-2-(4'-methoxy)-benzoylbenzoic Acid, prepared from the nitro compound by reduction with ferrous sulphate and ammonia in the

usual way, crystallised from absolute alcohol in needles, m.p. 186°. It gives bright red azo-compound when coupled with β -naphthol. It dissolves in alcohol with a yellow colour.

Condensation of Anisole with 4-Nitrophthalic Anhydride.

The anhydride (*cf.* Bogert and Boroschek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, **23**, 624; Mitter and Sircar, *loc. cit.*, p. 624) can be easily prepared by refluxing the nitro-acid with acetyl chloride for 1 hour. It does not require heating in vacuum at 190° until frothing ceases.

Aluminium chloride (40 g.) was gradually added to a well-stirred mixture of anhydride (20 g.) and redistilled anisole (200 c.c.) at 20-25°. The mixture was stirred for 2½ hours and then decomposed with powdered ice and dilute hydrochloric acid and the excess of anisole was distilled off with steam. The crystalline mass was repeatedly extracted with sodium carbonate and the filtrate acidified, when colourless shining needle-shaped crystals were obtained; yield, theoretical.

The crude acid (30 g.), after eight crystallisations from methyl alcohol, gave 2-(4'-methoxy)-benzoyl-4-nitrobenzoic acid of constant m.p. 217-18°. (Found: N, 4.73. $C_{15}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 4.66 per cent).

2-(4'-Methoxy)-benzoyl-5-nitrobenzoic Acid (2 g.) was obtained by diluting the methyl alcoholic mother liquor and repeated crystallisations (twelve times) from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 219-20°. (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{15}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 4.66 per cent).

Methyl-2-(4'-methoxy)-benzoyl-4-nitrobenzoate crystallised from ethyl acetate in shining plates, m.p. 178°. (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{16}H_{13}O_6N$ requires N, 4.5 per cent).

2-(4'-Methoxy)-benzoyl-4-aminobenzoic Acid, prepared by reducing the nitro-acid with ferrous hydroxide in the usual way, crystallised from water (charcoal) as yellow shining crystals, m.p. 156°, yield 0.2 g. (Found: N, 5.17. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 5.18 per cent).

2-(4'-Methoxy)-benzoyl-4-hydroxybenzoic Acid, prepared from the amino-acid as in the previous cases, was obtained as colourless needles from ethyl acetate and petroleum ether, m.p. 203°. (Found: C, 66.19; H, 4.6. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.17; H, 4.42 per cent).

2:6-Dihydroxyanthraquinone.—The crude anthraquinone, obtained as usual from the above hydroxymethoxy-acid, was demethylated as in the case of 1:6-dihydroxyanthraquinone and the product crystallised

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from alcohol, m.p. above 365° . It sublimes at $200-250^{\circ}/0.004$, mm. in yellow needles. It gives a yellow colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and yellowish red colour with alkali.

The *diacetyl* derivative crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. $221-25^{\circ}$ (*lit.* m.p. $220-29^{\circ}$).

Methyl-2-(4'-methoxy)-benzoyl-5-nitrobenzoate crystallised from ethyl acetate as shining plates, m.p. 188° . (Found: N, 4.8. $C_{16}H_{13}O_6N$ requires N, 4.5 per cent).

2-(4'-Methoxy)-benzoyl-5-aminobenzoic Acid was obtained by reducing the corresponding nitro-acid with ferrous sulphate and ammonia. It crystallised from water (charcoal) as colourless needles, m.p. 160° . (Found: N, 5.33. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 5.2 per cent).

2-(4'-Methoxy)-benzoyl-5-hydroxybenzoic Acid was obtained by diazotising a fine suspension of the hydrochloride in water and the precipitated diazo-salt was decomposed by boiling. It crystallised from ethyl acetate and petroleum ether as colourless microscopic crystals, m.p. 225° , yied 0.3 g. from 2 g. of amino-acid. (Found: C, 66.35; H, 4.7. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.17; H, 4.41 per cent).

2:7-Dihydroxyanthraquinone, prepared as in the case of 1:6-dihydroxyanthraquinone, crystallised from alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. above 330° (diacetyl derivative, m.p. $189-91^{\circ}$). It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with bluish red colour in the cold and a deep red colour when heated. It dissolves in alkali with deep red colour.